

Engagement and Representation in STEM: Active Learning from the Perspective of Undergraduate Extension Students

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Abstract

Gender inequality in the exact sciences and engineering remains a global challenge. The *Meninas Velozes* Program seeks to address this issue through active learning methods and strategies, encouraging girls' participation in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) within an integrated STEAM approach. The inclusion of the Arts ("A" in STEAM) promotes creativity, critical thinking and interdisciplinary connections, reinforcing the relevance of these fields to students' lived experiences and broadening the appeal of science and technology learning. This study analyzes the impact of the pedagogical workshops developed by the Program, incorporating the perspectives of undergraduate students and the results of assessments applied to elementary school girls from public schools in Brasília, Brazil. The methodology is based on action research and includes active learning strategies such as flipped classrooms, problem-based learning and gamification. The workshops were structured into three categories: (i) integration and motivation; (ii) STEM/STEAM activities; and (iii) study organization and project presentation. Undergraduate students acted as tutors, promoting a collaborative environment and encouraging active participation. The results indicate that the workshops increased the students' interest in STEM and strengthened their self-confidence and sense of belonging. The undergraduate tutors emphasized that the intersectional and contextualized approach helps to reduce structural barriers by integrating academic content with students' social and cultural realities. Their presence as facilitators further increased female representation in these fields, promoting a cycle of inspiration and support. It is concluded that active learning approaches, combined with representation and ongoing support, are essential for girls' engagement in STEM. The results reinforce the need for educational policies that promote and expand similar initiatives.

Keywords: STEAM, STEM, active learning, gender equity

1 Introduction

Since childhood, individuals belonging to a society go through a process of acculturation, where their behavior and personality are mostly conditioned according to the characteristics considered normal for their biological sex. In the Brazilian context, the socialization of girls is in line with what Bell Hooks says in "Feminism Is for Everybody: Passionate Politics" they are given a role of subordination, being taught to be docile, attentive and to avoid confrontation (Hooks, 2018, p. 35), and there is also a notion that personal value is linked to their physical appearance and how useful they are to others. These constraints have a profound impact on girls' and women's choices regarding the careers they consider possible to enter, an effect that intensifies when we talk about public elementary school students, such as the participants in the *Meninas Velozes* Program in the city of *Santa Maria - DF*, which has, according to data provided by the Federal District Planning Company, a worrying Multidimensional Poverty Index (Gonçalves, 2015). In addition to financial vulnerability, there are other barriers that are invisible to the naked eye, but which are well known and prevent them from seeing themselves facing the common challenges of STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) careers. We're talking about low self-esteem, self-sabotage and a lack of representation and encouragement within the community to which they belong. It can be seen that even after all the movement to promote women in higher education, we see a disparity in the number of men and women in STEM areas, with a total of 34% female participation in Brazil (Nascimento et al., 2023, p. 5), something far from the minimum parity threshold of 45% established by UNESCO (2017).

In this context, the *Meninas Velozes* Program stands out for promoting workshops with active learning strategies aimed at elementary school students in the Federal District, relying on the direct work of tutors from different areas of knowledge, such as Mechanical Engineering, Forestry Engineering, Chemical Engineering, Production Engineering, Anthropology, Pedagogy, Social Sciences and Communication. These tutors lead the teaching process, and are also primarily responsible for designing, mediating, and carrying out the activities. These responsibilities drive the development of essential skills in undergraduates, such as autonomy, communication, teamwork, leadership, and the ability to plan and coordinate educational activities. In addition to the aspects mentioned above, little is known about how the tutors themselves perceive the impact of active learning on the trajectory of the participants, especially in relation to awakening interests in STEM areas. The aim of this work is to understand how the tutors of the *Meninas Velozes* Program perceive the impact of their actions in developing workshops using active learning to promote STEM areas among elementary school students in the Federal District.

1.1 Overview of the Meninas Velozes Program

The *Meninas Velozes* Program is an initiative of the Faculty of Technology, in partnership with the Faculty of Education and the Faculty of Science and Technology in Engineering, of the University of Brasilia (UnB), to help reduce gender inequality in the areas of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM), promoting female protagonism from primary to higher education. Composed of two research projects and four extension projects, the program involves actions based on pedagogical workshops, mentoring, events, and interactive activities. These initiatives aim to awaken girls' and women's interest in STEM areas and deconstruct gender stereotypes while encouraging the development of socio-emotional skills and promoting a more inclusive academic and professional environment.

The STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics) approach used in the projects proposes an integrated and interdisciplinary way of teaching and learning by uniting these areas, with a focus on developing critical thinking, creativity, and collaborative problem-solving. It emerges as an inclusive alternative, integrating creativity, critical thinking, and interdisciplinarity to make science and technology more accessible to girls (Salehjee & Watts, 2023). The STEAM approach allows girls from different backgrounds to develop essential 21st century skills such as communication, innovation, collaboration, and problem-solving (Liao, Motter, & Patton, 2016, p. 29). This methodology also enables the re-signification of past experiences, strengthens present realities, and creates new future possibilities (Toliver, 2021, p. 133), thus contributing to a transdisciplinary education (Colucci-Gray, 2022). In the *Meninas Velozes* Program, this approach is applied within the workshops through tools such as the flipped classroom, hands-on activities, gamification of assessments, One-minute-paper and Think-Pair Share. These tools encourage the creation of creative solutions, such as the construction of prototypes, scientific experiments, and collective projects.

1.2 Active Learning in the context of Meninas Velozes Program

The banking education system is characterized by rigidity between the roles of teachers and students. The educator holds the knowledge and transmits the information unilaterally. The students are therefore vessels into which this content is passively poured, given their supposed lack of knowledge. A hierarchical silence is therefore maintained, centered on the quantitative transmission of information, with no sensitivity related to how this content is passed on (Freire, 1987). On the other hand, liberating or problematizing education understands students as subjects in their learning process, thus encouraging them to develop an autonomous way of understanding the world around them (Ferreira Paiva et al., 2017).

Thus, the student takes an active stance in challenging situations in which critical thinking, creativity, empowerment, and communication skills are valued and encouraged, while being fundamental to academic and civic development (Liao, Motter, & Patton, 2016; Salehjee & Watts, 2023). Thus, the active learning strategies applied by the *Meninas Velozes* undergraduate students focus on practicing liberating education and reinforcing the knowledge acquired by giving students autonomy and promoting meaningful learning (Tavares, 2010).

Workshops: In this pedagogical context, the “workshop” refers to a collective teaching and learning strategy, using everyday elements of the students throughout their learning process, with the aim of critically connecting theory and practice, stimulating active and collaborative student participation, developing critical and reflective thinking through the action-reflection-action cycle, and strengthening student autonomy and protagonism (Fornazari, & Obara, 2017). In the project, the “workshops” are group meetings between tutors, elementary school students, and teachers in which active learning activities take place.

In-class exercise: The in-class exercise is an applied strategy in which tutors suggest a question or challenge to students. In this case, groups of two to four students are formed, with one in each group responsible for taking notes during the discussion (Tasaka, & Neto, 2013). At the end of the lesson, the work is brought together for a collective debate that consolidates the content by exchanging ideas, correcting mistakes in real time and deepening learning. The practice encourages collaboration, logical reasoning and contextualized problem solving.

Flipped classroom: Another strategy commonly applied by the project is the Flipped Classroom, in which the content is previously presented to students via the internet. Tutors then provide students with support material (such as texts, activities, and recorded or selected videos), with the aim of developing a complementary activity in the classroom, either individually or collectively (Moreira, 2018). Thus, students are led to a “reflective doing”, which consists of practice followed by reflection on it, encouraging autonomy and initiative in their learning process, as well as promoting greater interaction between students, tutors and teachers (Moreira, 2018).

Think-Pair-Share: Another collaborative strategy used by the project and often mentioned in studies dealing with group teaching in the classroom. It is based on three pillars: time for reflection, time to talk with a colleague, and time to share with a larger group (dos Reis & Barreto, 2017). The strategy encourages critical thinking and collaboration by involving moments of individual reflection and group sharing, favoring engagement and the collective construction of knowledge.

Gamification: One of the strategies most used by the project is playful devices to engage and motivate students (Soprani, de Abreu Mól, & do Espírito Santo, 2025). Therefore, it consists of applying elements and dynamics that arouse students' interest, such as challenges and rewards, in order to instigate them to actively participate in their learning process by promoting engagement, creativity, and problem-solving. Within the project, gamification takes place mainly through the application of Quizzes, which are question-and-answer games, with the aim of consolidating the content immediately after the tutor's presentation.

One-minute-paper: A simple formative feedback technique applied during or after classroom activities. It summarizes students' perceptions of certain subjects and can describe something like “what I learned today” or “what I still don't understand.” This brief written reflection allows the student to mentally summarize the content and express doubts. It can encourage immediate revision of the content and provides tutors with information on the effectiveness of the lesson (Domokos & Huey, 2023).

Practical activities: These are based on learning from experience (Holstermann, Grube, and Bögeholz, 2010). This strategy strengthens students' connection with the content by contextualizing and individualizing learning, promoting retention, critical thinking, problem-solving, and active engagement, making knowledge more concrete and meaningful (Fornazari & Obara, 2017). In the project, these are the final activities of the workshop, after the student's exposure to the proposed topic. As such, the activity varies according to the topic, whether it's assembling electrical circuits, modeling systems for 3D printing, or making notebooks after a bookbinding lesson, for example.

1.3 Tutors as facilitators of knowledge construction in active learning contexts

Changing the learning process to a gender-sensitive STEAM approach requires a reframing of the roles of teachers and mediators. Instead of limiting themselves to the linear transmission of knowledge, these professionals become facilitators of the educational process, promoting new power relations and dynamics of engagement, breaking down traditional and inflexible structures (Pearson, & Somekh, 2006, p. 537). Thus, the teacher's role goes beyond giving instructions to rather create a dynamic environment where students take on leading roles in the construction of knowledge.

From the planning to the execution of activities, mediators play a strategic role in choosing authentic contexts and integrating innovative methodologies that favor the active participation of students (Bacich & Holanda, 2020). The mastery of different pedagogical practices and digital resources enhances this educational intention, ensuring a meaningful learning process connected to the realities and interests of students (Allen-Handy et al., 2020; Bacich & Holanda, 2020; Salehjee & Watts, 2023). Therefore, the mediating role of the educator becomes central in implementing effective teaching strategies, adapting processes according to students' needs, and strengthening students' autonomy (Pearson & Somekh, 2006; Bacich & Holanda, 2020).

While aiming for a gender-sensitive education, it is essential to create safe spaces that do not impose barriers to the growth and performance of STEM girls. In the *Meninas Velozes* Program, undergraduate tutors play an inspiring role by sharing their academic trajectories, cultural, and personal experiences. The interdisciplinary composition of the Program, which brings together fields from the humanities and engineering, enriches the training process, favoring the exchange of knowledge. This approach fosters identification between students, strengthens bonds, and significantly expands the possibilities for engagement with the sciences. The project thus contributes to building a more inclusive and diverse future for STEM subjects.

2 Research Design

This study adopted a qualitative approach based on critical educational action research, seeking not only to understand but also to continuously improve the pedagogical practices developed within the framework of the *Meninas Velozes* Program. Critical educational action research, in this context, was conceived as a cyclical and collaborative process in which the subjects involved, in this case the undergraduate tutors themselves, actively participated in the construction of knowledge, the identification of problems, and the proposal of improvements to the strategies used in the educational workshops (Koerich, 2009). The methodology combined three main fronts: (i) a narrative literature review, which provided the theoretical basis for the main guiding concepts of the Program, such as active learning, female participation in STEM areas, and inclusive pedagogical practices; (ii) the application of a digital questionnaire, constructed and analyzed jointly by the tutors; and (iii) a collaborative reflection with structured feedback, which is based on the agile *Start, Stop, Continue* methodology, aimed at critical evaluation and improvement of the pedagogical actions developed

2.1 Data Collection

A collaborative reflection session was held with the project monitors, with the aim of collectively reflecting on the pedagogical practices adopted, the effectiveness of the actions, and possible methodological improvements. The discussion made it possible to identify common perceptions, difficulties faced, and suggestions for improving the workshops. This qualitative discussion made it possible to identify patterns of perception, challenges faced, and proposals for improving workshops. The main data collection tool consisted of this guided reflection, combined with the results obtained through a digital questionnaire. The questionnaire was drawn up collectively by the undergraduate monitors, based on the demands observed during the project and anchored in the theoretical references that guide their practice. The purpose of this instrument was to promote a formative and reflective process among the participants.

The agile *Start, Stop, Continue* methodology guided this reflection, allowing tutors to identify practices that should be maintained, reformulated, or abandoned. This approach encouraged the development of analytical and self-reflective skills, as well as reinforcing the participatory nature of the research. This reflective process enriched the interpretation of the data and served as a space for continuing education for the participants, promoting alignment between theory and practice. The discussions raised strong points and aspects to be improved in the methodologies applied, contributing to the continuous improvement of the Program, leading to a formative, participatory, and transformative investigation in which the tutors in the research are both agents and analysts of their own pedagogical practice.

To systematize the pedagogical purposes guiding the process of collaborative reflection with the program's tutors, Table 1 below shows the main objectives of the activities carried out. The organization of the objectives seeks to highlight the methodological proposal of the *Meninas Velozes* Program and the formative, reflective, and investigative goals that guided the research.

Table 1. Active Learning Strategies' goals

Active Learning	Objective
Practical activities (hands-on)	Motivation, integration of theory and practice, autonomy, self-confidence to build new things.
One minute paper (new technique)	Reflection on theory/practice, survey of successes/mistakes, improvement of workshops.
Gamefication	Fun, additional motivation, incentive and participation (boost engagement).
Classroom exercises (Quizzes + Questions)	Engagement in the classroom.
Flipped classroom	Prior preparation, time optimization, connection with the topic, and autonomy.
Think-Pair-Share	Interaction, collective construction, exchange of knowledge, dialog / self-exposure, courage.

3 Results

Table 2 was drawn up from the discussion among the five tutors. In it, it was possible to identify perceptions about the application of active learning strategies and whether they effectively engage students in STEM. We also analyzed the effectiveness of the practices and tried to assess what should be improved, continued, or discontinued. They also came up with ideas for practices that could be implemented. This meeting proved to be an organizational opportunity for the Program and a fruitful alignment between the monitors. In addition, considering the integrative nature of the workshops, the techniques are applied together, which directs the analysis to a macro view in such a way that the development of one technique affects the development of others. Based on this reflection, the activities carried out in the project were evaluated, a summary of which can be seen in the table below.

Table 2. Active Learning Strategies - Structured Feedback through *Start, Stop and Continue*

Active Learning	Start	Stop	Continue
Flipped classroom	Recall topics from the flipped classroom before the presentation / Test playful elements (songs, movies, series)	Assume that basic concepts have already been understood in advance of the lesson / Send the lesson at short notice	Rewarding access to the flipped classroom / Bringing in interesting stories and aspects
Classroom exercises (Quizzes + Questions)	Adding anti-stress meditation breaks / Promoting integration at the start of the workshops with students and monitors, seeking out their experiences	Applying replication exercises, without time for reflection	Add more questions to the reflection and interaction workshop long / Bring the questions closer to the girls' reality
Gamefication	Integrate activities more and promote greater student participation / value them at the end of the year	Broadening collective participation	Integrate other methodologies with gamification / Continue with rewards
Practical activities (hands-on)	Structure workshops to allow time for discovery / train monitors to replicate workshops	Promotion of execution workshops, without reflection on the process	Increase the explanation of why and the importance of the content / bring in more activities that generate some physical souvenir product
Think-Pair-Share	Separate the groups to avoid segregation and better integrate the students	-	Do more group activities for exchanges, dialogues and gamification activities
One minute paper (new technique)	Meetings to reflect on the workshops between monitors (once a month) and with students (twice a year)	-	Open up more spaces for feedback (from students and monitors)

3.1 Discussion of Results – Collaborative Reflection with Structured Feedback: Start, Stop, Continue.

The flipped classroom approach is implemented with the aim of preparing students for the activities to be developed in class and optimizing the time available with them. Thus, the class proceeds under the assumption that all students have understood the basic concepts presented in the preparatory material. However, this is not always fully achieved and can sometimes result in reduced fluidity during the lesson. Consequently, the importance of reviewing the key concepts at the beginning of class was emphasized, in order to ensure a common level of understanding among students. Furthermore, the incorporation of engaging content such as music and films was highlighted by the tutors as a strategy that can motivate students to engage with the suggested material in the flipped classroom format, and it is of interest to the tutors to implement this approach. Another practice to be further developed is the timely preparation and distribution of the flipped classroom reference materials, so that students have more time to study the content in advance. Regarding the practices that have been successfully implemented, the tutors noted the value of integrating historical and interesting facts into the presentation, as well as incorporating gamification elements into the flipped classroom. An example of this includes rewarding students who completed the preparatory work at home.

Regarding the in-class exercises, similar issues and solutions were identified as those observed in the hands-on activities. In this case, in addition to the importance of connecting the students' realities to the content being studied and organizing the session time to foster autonomous reflection, the discussion also highlighted the importance of incorporating breaks during the activities. It was thus collectively concluded that it would be valuable to include moments of interaction between the students and the tutors at the beginning of the sessions, not only to strengthen group integration but also to promote moments of relaxation and lightness, which are essential in the context of a fast-paced, productivity-driven society in which these students are immersed.

Gamification, on the other hand, refers to an element present in the workshops, and is developed at specific moments through quizzes, for example. In this case, the importance of integrating the activities into the students' context outside the classroom was identified, in order to enhance the value of participation and engagement. One idea raised during a discussion among the monitors was to award prizes at the end-of-year event that value the students' engagement on social networks, for example. At the same time, in gamification dynamics, individual participation is currently more valued. In this context, the monitors pointed out the importance of promoting gamification dynamics that are also collective, to better integrate the students with each other.

Regarding the hands-on activities, the importance of giving the students more time to make their own discoveries was highlighted, as well as allowing them to reflect on and resolve errors in carrying out the proposed activities, rather than directly reproducing the instructions. At the same time, explaining the connection between the content and its real-life applications was collectively identified as something effective for the students' learning. In addition, another motivating factor is the construction, during the workshops, of artifacts that can be kept by the students, which was pointed out as a positive practice in promoting the engagement of these students. On the other hand, it was observed that making these artifacts generates empowerment due to the accomplishment of an unprecedented task.

Regarding Think-Pair-Share, we identified the importance of this dynamic for the socialization and integration of the students, to engage them collectively in the proposed activity. However, the groups are defined by the students themselves, which limits integration between students who are not friends outside the project. The monitors therefore pointed out the importance of starting to intervene in this group formation, to promote greater integration between all the students.

The One Minute Paper technique was implemented recently and has already shown promise. In this case, feedback was encouraged to be given manually after the hands-on stage. Thus, the promotion of a feedback space for the students resulted in opinions guiding the project, indicating what was positively or negatively received by the students. This result led to a consensus among the monitors on the importance of holding periodic reflective meetings in the project to internally evaluate the activities carried out and better integrate

the monitors and students in the project. As well as bringing about a self-reflection of the students' learning from the activities carried out.

To shed more light on the benefits of the methodologies, the following are testimonies from elementary school pupils that explain the positive impact and self-perception of the active learning strategies used in the workshops. Regarding the robotics and programming workshop, the following feedback was obtained: "I felt very happy, a new experience for me. I'm very interested in programming, and I had fun trying to write the code." , "I feel smart for having managed to assemble the protoboard; it wasn't as difficult as it seemed at first; it was really nice." , "I felt good, happy and excited to be able to understand something I never thought I would." and "I felt proud of myself and also of the colleague who did it with me." In addition, the following is a comment made by another student at the same workshop:

At first I felt helpless and lacked basic knowledge, but after the protoboard started working I was very happy and understood that help is sometimes needed. I did it with my friend, and group (or pair) work is important and sometimes fun. In short, I felt like a DIVA! (Primary school student)

4 Conclusion

Gender inequality in STEM fields is still a global challenge, and this study aimed to understand how the tutors of the *Meninas Velozes* Program perceive the impact of their actions in developing workshops using active methodologies to promote STEM fields among elementary school students in the Federal District. The analysis provided greater clarity regarding the practical application of active learning methodologies, contributing to the improvement of pedagogical planning and fostering a qualified debate on the importance of representativeness and intentionality in educational actions aimed at gender equity in STEM.

The study showed that the active learning approaches, as flipped classroom, classroom exercises, gamification, practical activities, peer learning, and one-minute paper, are methods with great potential for improving teaching and learning when applied to the students' reality. The tutors also made significant gains in terms of the students' engagement, empowerment, and autonomy in their own training process by acting as mediators and facilitators of knowledge.

The agile methodology of Start, Stop, Continue allows us to observe the active learning methodologies that are most effective for the Program, as well as reinforcing the participatory and investigative nature of the project. A key point that emerged was the importance of intentionality in active learning, and also in the choice of physical and symbolic spaces in which learning takes place. Welcoming, interactive, and safe spaces contribute decisively to building bonds and promoting female protagonism in the workshops.

The students' spontaneous reports show their self-perception and confidence, showing that when they feel capable of carrying out new tasks, they recognize themselves as the protagonists of their own learning process. In this way, it can be concluded that active learning, when applied with pedagogical intent, sensitivity and listening, becomes powerful tools for building a more innovative education.

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